

Paper for Reading Report

English Class

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Object;

Cesario Zifa Harlan Alif Junior's paper, *The Moral Content of Les' Copaque Cartoon Showing Upin dan Ipin in Character Forming*

Background and Analysis

Abstract

The purpose of this project is to examine and describe the moral values in Upin and Ipin films. Including descriptive research with content analysis method. The data is taken from the contents of the Upin cartoon film and secondary data from several uploads from previous research and the internet. The results of the study reveal that Upin and Ipin films have various moral values, including respect, courage, tolerance, honesty, holding back, sharing, forgiving each other, helping, and thanking. This cartoon is highly recommended to be watched by children for the formation of children's character because it contains moral values that are in accordance with the nation's culture because it contains moral values that are in accordance with the nation's culture.

Conclusion

The Upin and Ipin cartoon show is one of the most complete cartoon shows, with implicit moral content to the point of having simple jokes that can make it the best-selling cartoon show in Malay land. The use of the content analysis method is expected to provide an overall exposure to Upin and Ipin cartoons.

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Article/Media/Literacy Resources based Questions:

1) Is it available data or information to answer it,

Yes, it is based on *Les' Copaque's* scenes source.

2) Is the data or information is obtained through scientific methods, such as interviews, observations, questionnaires, documentation, participation, and evaluations/tests,

In some parts of the research, it contained scientific method

3) Does it meet the originality requirements, identified through previous research mapping (state of the arts),

Yes, it does. Because I'm pretty sure that my paper is already avoided by plagiarism and to increase the awareness from the negative aspect of the television shows

4) Does it make a significant theoretical contribution to the development of science,

In some part of my paper, I'm sure it does

5) Does it regard controversial and unique issues that are currently happening,

No, it doesn't

6) The problem requires an answer and an immediate solution, but the answer is not yet known to the general public, and

Yes, as I researched that *Upin dan Ipin* shows is good for being watch by children

7) The problem is posed within the limits of the researcher's interest (field of study) and ability.

Yes, because I'm concerned that spectacle that is appropriate for kids nowadays is decreasing

8) What developments or shifts were taking place at the time the event occurred,

The government is increasingly paying attention to appropriate shows for kids nowadays

9) What are the benefits of this research for the development of science and society at large in the future?

Pay more attention to the spectacle that is appropriate for future kids

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